

Validation of Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) for meteorological drought Risk in Central India

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Abstract

This study materialized an approach to drought risk (DR) mapping in an agricultural basin. The risks of drought have potential to cause damage, their occurrences are matter of concern to the agricultural society and economy. This study mainly dealt with droughts during the southwest monsoon season (June–September) in central India. The risk associated with drought was assessed by a combination of the regional exposure associated with natural events and the vulnerability of anthropogenic events. DR is the abstraction of the product of drought hazard (DH) and drought vulnerability (DV). The frequency of drought events has been computed using the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI). As the variability of rainfall is much higher than that of other variables, it makes SPI suitable for the analysis in this study.

Resulting area affected by drought based on 6 months base period has maximum area under dry condition that reflects the deficiency of water in stream flow and reservoir storage condition. The hazard map is then produced by occurrence probability of drought at respective stations. The application of GIS has played a vital role for analyzing, managing and representing DH, DV and computing DR in this study. Further, results of SPI have been validated with Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI) which is worldwide accepted as a global drought calculator.

Keywords: Meteorological drought, Standardized Precipitation Index, GIS, Standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index, Drought hazard/Vulnerability/Risk, SPI validation.

Introduction

In India, precipitation is regarded as the primary source of water resource and, therefore, most planning and designing of water resource projects are based on the historical pattern of water availability and demand. Agriculture and related sectors of India are crucially dependent on the timely availability of adequate amount of water⁷. Drought has been defined by the World Meteorological Organization as a period of abnormally dry weather sufficiently prolonged for the lack of precipitation to cause a serious hydrological imbalance.

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A prolonged and severe water deficit can potentially cause major environmental, social and economic problems. The World Meteorological Organization¹⁹ reported that in the 25 years from 1967 to 1991 about 1.4 billion people were affected by drought and 1.3 million people were killed due to direct and indirect cause of drought²⁰.

Drought cannot be prevented but a lot can be done to reduce the impacts through preparedness and mitigation measures. Drought is considered by many researchers to be the most complex but least understood of all-natural hazards, affecting more people than any other hazard. Sivakumar¹⁵ and Pai et al¹² emphasized that the rainfall is the primary factor that leads to the generation and maintenance of drought conditions. According to Khadr et al⁸, drought characteristics are recognized as important factors in water resources planning and management. Within the hydrological cycle droughts are comprehensively explained by Tallaksen et al¹⁷.

Defining index is a method of deriving “value added” information related to drought by comparing current conditions to historical information based upon statistical computations. Several drought indices can be used to estimate the possible evolution of an on-going drought in order to adopt appropriate mitigation measures and drought policies for water resources management. This is because a drought index is expressed by a numeric number, which is believed to be far more functional than raw data during decision-making. Among them, SPI aims to provide a concise overall picture of drought, regardless to the actual probability distribution of the observed cumulative amounts of rainfall for a given time scale.

The changes in drought frequency, persistence and severity can be computed using the SPI. Many researchers including Barros et al³, Cancelliere et al⁴, Friedman⁵, Goyal⁶, Rajput et al¹³ and Richard et al¹⁴ have applied SPI extensively in many agricultural basins to identify the major dimensions of a drought: duration, intensity, severity, magnitude and frequency.

To manage the effect of probable drought, the knowledge of SPI alone is limited as it gives only the characteristic feature of the meteorological drought. Though it can be conveniently utilized as Hazard indicator of the area of application, but the susceptibility of an area to the impact of drought is to be addressed by the vulnerability of the region to the hazard. The risk of drought for a region not only depends on the natural hazard but also the associated

vulnerability with it. To minimize the effects of disasters, it is required to take appropriate measures to reduce vulnerability rather than risk.

Developing vulnerability profiles for regions and communities will provide critical information on who is at risk, the nature of risk and the reasons for such risk. To prolong this concept, we applied this approach with the use of application of GIS to an agriculture basin called Upper Seonath Sub-basin which is a part of the Mahanadi River basin in central India.

Material and Methods

In this study, to assess drought risk, a conceptual model as suggested by NDMC (National Drought Mitigation Centre) at the University of Nebraska-Lincoln in by which drought risk was defined as a product of drought hazard (DH) and drought vulnerability (DV), was applied¹⁸.

Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) has been used for the quantification of drought hazard. SPI is a tool developed by McKee et al⁹ for defining and monitoring local droughts. The index is computationally simple and is time-flexible. To determine the rarity of a drought at a given time scale of interest for any rainfall station with historical data is used to compute the occurrence probability. McKee et al^{9,10} assumed an aggregated precipitation gamma distribution and used a maximum likelihood method to estimate the parameters of the distribution. The gamma distribution is defined by its frequency or probability density function:

$$g(x) = \frac{1}{\beta^\alpha \Gamma(\alpha)} e^{-\frac{x}{\beta}} \frac{x^{\alpha-1}}{\beta}, \text{ for } x > 0 \quad (1)$$

where α , β and x are shape, scale and precipitation parameter respectively.

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^{\infty} y^{\alpha-1} e^{-y} dy \quad (2)$$

Here $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the gamma function. The alpha and beta parameters of the gamma probability density function are estimated for each station, for each time scale of interest (3 months, 6 months, 9 months etc.) and for each month of the year.

In this study, weights and ratings were assigned based on the cumulative probability using the severity. SPI has been applied extensively in many parts of the world including the United States²⁰, Australia³, Europe⁴ and Africa¹². The drought hazard then can be quantified based on the probability of drought occurrence.

For developing effective drought management measures, vulnerability information is required at a disaggregated level. Construction and use of composite indices from multi-dimensional data for measuring spatial differentials in social and economic development issues have been widely practiced and these techniques were explored in the current

study to address agricultural drought vulnerability. The spatial distribution of agricultural drought vulnerability provides certain valuable insights into the current agricultural situation of the study area.

Study Area: The study area Upper Seonath sub-basin (USB) is situated inside the Seonath basin of well-known Mahanadi River basin in Chhattisgarh. Entire study area of USB falls within the state of Chhattisgarh. The two districts of Chhattisgarh State namely Durg and Rajnandgaon are covered in this basin (figure 1). The USB is located between 20°16' N to 22°41' N latitude and 80°25' E to 82°35' E longitude with 7292 km² area of spread out of which agricultural land occupies 62.16% of total geographical area. The climate is tropical; it is hot and humid because of its proximity to the Tropic of Cancer and its dependence on the monsoons for rains. Summer temperatures can reach 45 °C (figure 2). Winters are pleasant with low temperatures and less humidity.

Seonath river system is marked by several dams, anicuts raised over almost its every tributary resulting in breakage in flow and drying up of the river during non-monsoon months. The southwest monsoon sets over this region during the second week of June and rainfall activity continuous till second week of October². The mean annual rainfall in the basin varies from 1005mm to 1255mm.

Data acquisition and application: Base maps, basin boundary and ancillary data were acquired from Bhuvan India website (<http://bhuvan.nrsc.gov.in>). These maps were either directly downloaded in a vector format or digitised in GIS platform within ArcGIS 10.3 software. Present village level population data and land-use data were generated from the imageries downloaded from Bhuvan web portal. The resulting maps are shown in figure 5. The study area is classified into six land-use classes. Total geographical area of USB is 7292 Km² out of which agricultural land occupies 4533 Km² which is about 62.16% of total geographical area; built up area occupies Km² i.e. 3.92% of total area, forest occupies Km² area i.e. 20.14% of total area and Tree clad occupies Km² i.e. 3.60% of total area which has minimum area in USB, waste land occupies 472 Km². i.e. 6.47% of total area, water bodies occupy 270 Km² which is about 3.70% of total geographical area.

The factors considered for influencing the drought vulnerability are land use and population density. Weighted average is taken to identify drought vulnerability index in ArcGIS software. Similarly, the meteorological data were collected from WRIS India (<http://www.india-wris.nrsc.gov.in>). Total 22 rain gauge stations (figure 1 and table 1) were selected and daily time series data from 1983 to 2013 was collected for this analysis.

To implement this concept quantitatively, two composite maps of Drought Hazard (DH) and Drought Vulnerability (DV) were produced. Finally, Drought Risk map (DRM) was

produced by multiplying drought hazard with drought vulnerability. The higher is the value of anyone between DH and DV, the higher is DR. This approach provides an important perspective on drought risk by obtaining information from those who experience the vulnerability and by examining links between the hazard, the impacts and ways to mitigate the impacts.

To validate the hazard map which is based on the value of SPI, it was compared with the SPEI by linear regression correlation analysis. The SPEI captures the main impact of increased temperatures on water demand. A serially complete data set of both temperature and precipitation is needed to calculate the SPEI. The SPEI basev2.0 uses the FAO-56 Penman–Monteith equation with a value for PET, the difference between the precipitation and PET for every month is computed¹. These provide measure of the water surplus or deficit for the analyzed month.

To find out the correlation, a scatter plot was plotted between SPI and SPEI. The strength of the linear association between two variables is quantified by the correlation coefficient R^2 . This value represents the fraction of the variation in one variable that may be explained by the other variable.

Results and Discussion

This study begins with emphasis on the extreme outlier of the monthly rainfall data that will provide the information about the lower outlier. Based on this analysis, years 1988, 1998, 2002 and 2009 are identified as the deficit years as shown in the mean monthly rainfall plot shown in figure 3.

Hazard assessment based on SPI: In this study the drought hazard in the USB has been assessed by reconstructing historical occurrences of droughts at varying time steps and drought categories by employing the SPI approach. The SPI computation has been applied to long-term precipitation data at 22 stations for the period 1983–2013 (January 1983 to December 2013). The occurrences in varying drought categories at 3, 6 and 9-month time steps are analysed. The 3 and 6-month SPI may give incomplete idea of dryness in the region where it is normally dry for a 6-month period.

Hence it is important to have a drought index for longer time scales as well; there is a possibility of a normal 3-month period occurring in the middle of a longer-term drought which would only be visible at longer timescales. Time series of long-term records (1983–2013) of monthly precipitation data at each station in the upper Seonath sub-basin is used as input to the SPI program.

Considering the three cases of time scales (3, 6 and 9 months), three extreme drought events ($SPI < -2$) occurred around five stations (Kharkhara, Selud, Doundi, Dongargaon and Madiyan) in the case of SPI₃, whereas in the case of SPI₆, three extreme drought events were evident around four stations (Kharkhara, Selud, Doundi and Madiyan) and two extreme drought events occurred in three

stations (Kharkhara, Selud and Madiyan) during the recorded period.

The years 1988, 1998, 2002 and 2009 having 54.54%, 50%, 50% and 50% of stations under condition drier than moderate dry condition respectively (table 3) and rest of the stations of year 1988, 1998, 2002 and 2009 are under near normal condition on drier side. To represent the spatial extent of dry condition of point SPI data, maps are prepared using spatial interpolation in GIS.

Figure 4 shows the areal extent of the drought categories in the month of September based on 3, 6 and 9 months' time scale respectively. The year 2002 is found to be the worst year, when about 67% of the total area of the basin was under drought. The calculated SPI is then used to calculate the probability of drought occurrence by assigning the rating on the drought severity as near normal rate = 1.0, moderate dry rate = 2.0, very dry rate = 3.0 and extremely dry rate = 4.0 (table 2). The drought hazard map is then produced by interpolation in ArcGIS as shown in the figure 6.

Drought vulnerability assessment: The vulnerability map is produced by selecting the drought vulnerability factor as land use and population density which are assumed to be two most vulnerable parameters to the drought in USB. The weighted average of both the parameters will be mapped in ArcGIS (figure 5). This analysis gives the vulnerable area as depicted in figure 7.

Drought Risk assessment: With the conceptual model used in this study, the assessment of drought risk using observed data was done. The drought risk was assessed by the product of drought hazard (DH) with drought vulnerability (DV) and mapped Drought Risk across USB. The extraction of knowledge from resulted risk map (figure 8) may be difficult due to its spatial variability. Hence, the resulted map has been reclassified on the basis of Bock area of the USB. The zonal_statistics tool has been used to prepare the map. The drought hazard index map was produced for 15 blocks as shown in figure 9.

Validation of SPI results with SPEI: SPI is only based on precipitation without considering temperature and evaporation which play an increasingly important role in drought occurrence because of global warming. The SPEI was developed by not only considering the sensibility of droughts to temperature but also remaining the multiple timescales and allowing for flexible comparability.

The calculation of SPEI is based on the water balance equation. SPEI has been widely used in drought monitoring and characterization at the global and regional scales. SPEI is used to validate the SPI results by determining the correlation coefficient which shows good correlation between SPEI and SPI as depicted in the figure 10.

Figure 1: Location map of the study area

Figure 2: Mean monthly rainfall, maximum and minimum temperature (Data Set: 1983-2013: 22 Station)

Figure 3: Monthly rainfall distribution and boxplot (Data Set: 1983-2013: 22 Station)

Table 1
Rain gauge station information and data specifications

S.N.	Station	Lat.	Long.	Operated by	Gauging type	Parameters	Data Scale
1	Admabad	20.70	81.23	SWRD	Tipping bucket Rain gauge	RF	Daily
2	Ambagarh_Chowki	20.78	80.75	SWRD		RF	Daily
3	Balod	20.73	81.23	SWRD		RF	Daily
4	Bhanupratappur	20.32	81.08	SWRD		RF	Daily
5	Bhatagaon	20.95	81.40	SWRD		RF	Daily
6	Bhilai	21.20	81.42	SWRD		ALL	Daily
7	Dhamdha	21.45	81.25	SWRD		RF	Daily
8	Dongargaon	20.98	80.86	SWRD		RF	Daily
9	Dongargarh	21.18	80.77	SWRD		RF	Daily
10	Doundi	20.48	81.10	SWRD		RF	Daily
11	Doundi Lohara	20.79	81.06	SWRD		RF	Daily
12	Durg	21.22	81.28	SWRD		ALL	Daily
13	Gondly	20.75	81.13	SWRD		RF	Daily
14	Gundardehi	20.97	81.29	SWRD		RF	Daily
15	Gurur	20.70	81.41	SWRD		RF	Daily
16	Khapri	21.03	81.40	SWRD		RF	Daily
17	Kharkhara	20.97	81.03	SWRD		RF	Daily
18	Madiyan	21.13	80.58	SWRD		RF	Daily
19	Mohala	20.58	80.55	SWRD		RF	Daily
20	Patan	21.04	81.55	SWRD		RF	Daily
21	Selud	21.08	81.33	SWRD		RF	Daily
22	Seonath_Sigdei	21.05	81.04	SWRD		RF	Daily

Figure 4: Drought hazard severity based on SPI3, SPI6 and SPI9 using 30 year time series

Figure 5: Drought Hazard map of USB

Figure 6: Land-use map and population density map of the USB

Figure 7: Drought Vulnerability map of USB

Figure 8: Drought Risk map of USB

Figure 9: Block level drought risk map of USB

Table 2
Drought classification (Severity) based on SPI

SPI Value	Class
> 2	(EW) Extremely Wet
1.5 to 1.99	(VW) Very Wet
1.0 to 1.49	(MW) Moderately Wet
-0.99 to +0.99	(NN) Near Normal
-1.0 to -1.49	(MD) Moderately Dry
-1.5 to -1.99	(VD) Very Dry
< -2.0	(ED) Extremely Dry

Table 3
Result Drought Characteristics of the USB

Year	1988			1998			2002			2009		
	3	6	9	3	6	9	3	6	9	3	6	9
Stations affected	9	12	11	5	11	11	6	10	10	4	10	11
Duration (months)	11	8	12	7	7	11	6	6	11	4	6	6
Magnitude	-13.2	-17.8	-19.3	-7.95	-10.1	-11.1	-9.2	-13.07	-14.53	-5.57	-8.36	-6.97
Intensity (per month)	-1.2	-2.2	-1.6	-1.1	-1.4	-1	-1.5	-2.2	-1.3	-1.4	-1.4	-1.2
Severity	MD	ED	SD	MD	MD	MD	MD	ED	MD	MD	MD	MD

Figure 10: Validation of SPI with SPEI - Scatter plot with linear regression line (in blue)

Conclusion

To delineate an implementable drought mitigation strategy, risk areas are to be identified based on historical records to establish priority zones for comprehensive and integrated development programmes aimed at drought proofing and mitigation. Mitigation can be scientifically equated with resistance as a combination of avoidance, tolerance and resilience¹⁶. To aid in understanding spatiotemporal occurrence and patterns of agro-climatic variables, accurate and inexpensive quantitative approaches such as GIS application and long-term data are used.

Disaster resilient societies should primarily focus on identification, quantification and ranking of vulnerability status. Under this back ground, the current study has showcase systematic approach for measuring and ranking drought vulnerability as well as risk. A closer examination of risk map and its component maps may provide more insights to the drought managers to target interventions effectively. Novelty lies in the development of adaptive capacity based on the key indicators of drought vulnerability. It was revealed that the rainfall is not uniform throughout the year in this study area.

Results showed that the year 1988, 1998, 2002 and 2009 are the years which were severely affected. To reduce the drought vulnerability of the affected regions, it is vital to truly comprehend spatio-temporal drought patterns and their subsequent impacts.

Southwest monsoon season (June–September) contributes about 75–90% of the total annual rainfall and at the end of September. If the area is suffering from drought; it means the entire year will maintain dry condition. To cop up with the drought, farmers can diversify their cropping practices using a mix of crop species both in space and time, growing different cultivars at different sowing dates, combining less productive drought-resistant cultivars with high-yielding but water-sensitive crops.

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